

and fertilizer were followed. Rice yield, weed species, and weed weights were determined at harvest.

Results are shown in the table. Whether direct-seeded or transplanted, the high yielding variety BR3 outyielded the local variety. When transplanted, it produced 31% more yield than when direct-seeded. The local variety had lower yields because of its low tillering rate when transplanted; however, it yielded 40% more when direct-seeded.

Weeds were a problem in the direct-seeded plots. The control plot had significantly lower yields, 39% less than the herbicide-treated and hand-weeded

plots.

The best treatment combined a low dose of herbicide and hand weeding. Although the yield it gave did not differ significantly from that of hand weeding, it was better than that of any of the three herbicide treatments. In Bangladesh, the combination of a low dose of herbicide and weeding would be practical and would complement the existing hand-weeding methods.

The transplanted plot had less weed infestation and showed no significant reduction in yield between the control and the herbicide-alone plots. A low dose of herbicide plus hand weeding, however,

increased yields by 9% over the control. The cultural practice of puddling plus the competitive advantage of the transplanted rice plant over weeds greatly reduced weed problems where water management was good.

The weed species present in the BR3 and Dharial plots differed. In BR3 the sedges *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus difformis*, and *Fimbristylis littoralis* were the major weeds. In the plots of the taller Dharial, sedge growth was much reduced, and the grass *Echinochloa crus-galli* was the dominant weed. Weed weights in the Dharial direct-seeded control plots were 92 g/m² compared with 133 g/m² in BR3.

Soil and crop management

Residual effect of blue-green algae application on rice yield

R. Jagannathan, S. Kannaiyan, and V. G. Palaniyandi, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

Field trials to determine the residual effect of blue-green algae for nitrogen fixation on rice yields were laid out using ADT31 during the 1975 and 1976 kar (July–Oct.) season and using IR20 during the 1975 and 1976 pishanam (Nov.–March) season. The treatments were 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, 25–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 25–25–25 kg/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, algae alone at 10 kg/ha, and the untreated control.

After four seasons, the same treatments were repeated during the 1977 kar and 1977–78 pishanam seasons, with no algae added. Withholding algae did not generally affect the yield trend much (see table). In the plots where algae alone were applied, however, yields decreased slightly in the 1977 kar season. The results indicate that the residual effects of application of blue-green algae for a continuous period of four seasons will provide sufficient inoculum for subsequent crops.

Effect of blue-green algae on rice yields, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	1977 kar season ^a		1977–78 pishanam season ^b	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)
0 NPK	3.3	–	4.8	–
0 NPK + blue-green algae	3.2	3.2	5.4	13.9
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.3	2.2	5.2	7.6
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha + blue-green algae	3.8	17.1	5.2	9.8
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.8	11.2	5.1	7.6
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha + 10 kg/ha blue-green algae	4.1	24.6	5.1	7.6
F test:	S		NS	
CD:	456		–	

^aJuly–October. ^bNovember–March.

Fertilizers for deep placement and slow release of nitrogen for rice

E. T. Craswell, visiting scientist, International Rice Research Institute, and P. L. G. Vlek, soil scientist, International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC), Muscle Shoals, Alabama, USA

Rice commonly uses only 30 to 40% of applied fertilizer nitrogen. A great deal of research has therefore been carried out to develop more efficient nitrogen fertilizer sources and management

practices.

Three major approaches that have been developed are split application, deep placement, and controlled release. The latter two approaches — as mudballs or urea supergranules and sulfur-coated urea, respectively — have frequently proven superior to split application of urea in experiments conducted in the 10 countries of the International Network on Fertilizer Efficiency in Rice.

A fourth approach combines the deep placement and slow-release concepts. A

Comparative effects of basal broadcast urea (BU), split urea (SU), supergranules (SG) of urea placed at 10-cm depth, basal broadcast sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and sulfur-coated supergranules of urea (SCSG) placed at 10cm depth on growth and nitrogen recovery by IR38 in the greenhouse.

Fertilizer ^a	Panicles (no.)	Dry matter (g/pot)		Apparent nitrogen recovery ^b (%)
		Grain	Total tops	
O	27	33	99	—
BU	31	38	123	28
SU	31	41	134	48
SG	31	45	151	69
SCU	34	46	140	56
SCSG	39	52	163	89

^aAll fertilizers were applied at the rate of 460 mg N/pot.

^bApparent N recovery = $\frac{\text{N uptake in fertilized plant} - \text{N uptake in control (mg)}}{460 \text{ mg}} \times 100\%$.

practical means of achieving such combination was provided by the

Fertilizer Technology Division of the International Fertilizer Development

Center (IFDC) in the form of sulfur-coated urea supergranules. Preliminary results obtained with this experimental material in a greenhouse study at IFDC headquarters in Alabama are reported here.

The table shows the mean data from two soils and two water regimes (which had only minor effects on rice growth). The results suggest that the combination of deep placement and slow release shows considerable promise for improving fertilizer efficiency.

The sulfur-coated supergranules of urea are being tested at IRRI in 1978 as part of a joint IRRI-IFDC project aimed at improving nitrogen fertilizer efficiency for rice.

Environment and its influence

Possible causes of a new physiological disorder of rice in Korea

J. H. Lee, postdoctoral fellow, and S. Yoshida, plant physiologist, International Rice Research Institute

New varieties derived from indica/japonica crosses have been successfully grown in the Republic of Korea. These short, lodging-resistant, and high-tillering varieties are now planted on 660,000 ha, about half of Korea's total rice land. Consequently, the national average rice yield in Korea reached 6.64 t/ha, the world's highest, in 1977.

Yushin, one of the best indica/japonica varieties, has many good characteristics and gives high yields under favorable weather and soil conditions. But in 1976, it suffered *sudden wilting* in farmers' fields while other varieties such as Tongil seemed healthy under similar or identical conditions. Subsequent investigations into this new physiological disorder suggested that low sunlight, excessive nitrogen application, and highly reductive soil conditions either singly or combined, might be possible causes of the disorder.

Some visual symptoms of *sudden wilting* are orange discoloration of leaves,

development of nodal roots above the soil surface, total root rot, and lodging. Those observations led to the hypothesis that suffocation of root tissues was a direct cause of the disorder.

The oxygen transport characteristics of Yushin, Tongil, and IR262 were examined by two methods. First, the number and size of the air spaces in each internode were investigated (see table). In the 5th internode from the top, all three varieties have a similar number of air spaces, although the air spaces of Tongil were larger. In the 4th internode, Tongil had 31 air spaces, Yushin had only 2, and one of Tongil's parents, IR262, had none. The observations indicated that the ability of Yushin and IR262 for oxygen transport is very limited compared with that of Tongil.

Second, soil-cultured plants of the three varieties were subjected to paraffin treatment. To decrease the oxygen supply from the air to root tissues through the soil-water system, a layer of liquid paraffin about 5 to 6 mm thick was applied to the water surface in the pots at 47 days after seeding. The experiment was repeated twice. Each time *sudden wilting* was observed on Yushin and IR262 at about 1 week after

the treatment, but Tongil remained green and healthy.

The findings suggest that Yushin has limited ability to transport oxygen. The limited oxygen supply may cause suffocation of root tissues, weaken metabolic activity of the tissues, and induce root rot, subsequently inducing *sudden wilting* and lodging under

Varietal difference in number and size of air spaces in the internodes of rice plants at the ripening stage. IRRI, 1978.

Internode position ^a	Air spaces	
	No.	Mean diameter (mm)
	<i>Tongil</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	31	0.15
5th	31	0.31
	<i>Yushin</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	2	—
5th	29	0.24
	<i>IR262</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	0	—
5th	31	0.24

^aFrom top of plant.